

A Rapid Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Nitrite in Water

D. P. S. RATHORE* and P. K. TARAFDER

Chemical Laboratory, Regional Centre for Exploration and Research, Atomic Minerals Division,
Department of Atomic Energy, Shillong-793 012

Manuscript received 10 June 1988, accepted 14 December 1988

A new colour reaction for the determination of nitrite in water is reported. Nitrite reacts with *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid in hydrochloric acid medium to form a diazonium cation, which is subsequently coupled with 8-hydroxyquinoline in alkaline medium to produce a reddish orange azo dye. The reactions are very fast and require no control of temperature. Features of this method include good sensitivity, rapidity, reproducibility, freedom from pH effects, temperature independence, less interference and ease of performance.

NITRITE when correlated with other forms of nitrogen in water can provide an index of organic pollution¹. The presence of nitrite ion in water is harmful as it causes methemoglobinemia and it acts as a precursor in the formation of *N*-nitrosamines, many of which have been shown to be potent carcinogens². It also affects the dissolved oxygen content of water.

Many analytical methods have been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of nitrite³⁻⁵. Most of the methods are based on Griess reaction, i.e. the formation of a azo dye by diazotisation of an aromatic amine with nitrite and subsequent coupling of the diazonium cation with an aromatic amine or phenol. Many of these methods give good sensitivity and selectivity but require close control of pH and temperature during the diazotisation step and a relatively longer coupling time. Recently, *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid has been used as a diazotisable amine together with *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride as coupling agent in the determination of nitrite⁶. Although in this method the sensitivity is high but it requires a longer coupling time. Moreover, *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride is reported to be carcinogenic⁷.

Based on considerations of simplicity, rapidity, colour stability, adherence to Beer's law and sensitivity, we propose a method using *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid as a diazotisable amine together with 8-hydroxyquinoline as a coupling agent in the micro determination of nitrite.

Experimental

Spectral measurements were made on a Varian 634-S double-beam spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm quartz cuvettes.

p-Aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid (98.1% purity, Evans Chemetics) was used as such. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

A stock solution of standard nitrite solution ($1000 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by dissolving dried sodium nitrite (0.3750 g) in distilled water (250 ml) and a pellet of sodium hydroxide was added to prevent liberation of nitrous acid followed by spectroscopic grade chloroform (1 ml) to inhibit bacterial growth⁸. The solution was diluted before use. *p*-Aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid solution (0.2%) was prepared by dissolving it in 0.45 *M* HCl and diluted with the same acid. 8-Hydroxyquinoline solution (0.4%) was prepared fresh by dissolving 8-hydroxyquinoline (0.4 g) in distilled water containing sodium hydroxide (4.0 g) and diluted with distilled water.

Procedure: A 0.2% *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid solution (1 ml) was added to the nitrite solution (containing 0.10–1.6 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of nitrite) (masking agent added if needed) followed by 0.4% 8-hydroxyquinoline solution (1 ml), and made up to the mark with distilled water. The colour developed immediately and remained stable upto 72 h. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 495 nm against reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

In the experiments 25 μg of nitrite was taken in a final volume of 25 ml.

Spectral studies: The coloured azo dye showed maximum absorption at 495 nm. The magnitude of absorption of the blank was found to increase slightly with ageing of the 8-hydroxyquinoline solution. The absorption of the reagent blank at 495 nm measured against distilled water, was in the range 0.002–0.010 depending on the age of 8-hydroxyquinoline solution. Thus, the slight absorption of the reagent blank at 495 nm indicated the need for all measurements to be made against the blank.

Choice of coupling agent: Coupling agents tested were resorcinol, catechol, α -naphthol, β -naphthol, tiron, chromotropic acid, salicylic acid, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene and 8-hydroxyquinoline. 8-Hydroxyquinoline gave the most useful results and was further studied.

Effect of 8-hydroxyquinoline concentration and alkalinity: To each of a series of nitrite solutions, 0.04–0.4% 8-hydroxyquinoline solution (1 ml) in 4% sodium hydroxide was added. The 0.4% solution showed the most effective results; a smaller volume decreased the absorbance by multiple coupling. Sodium hydroxide was used to dissolve the 8-hydroxyquinoline, as it is sparingly soluble in water. The optimum concentration of sodium hydroxide in the reagent was found by another set of experiments in which 8-hydroxyquinoline (0.4 g) was dissolved in 0.4–8.0% of sodium hydroxide solution (100 ml); the 4.0% solution gave the best result. The selected volume of this composite reagent was 1 ml.

Effect of *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid concentration: The effect of *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid concentration on the colour intensity was studied following the prescribed procedure and adding to a series of nitrite solutions 0.03–0.5% solutions of the acid (1 ml) in 0.45 M HCl. The results showed a 0.2% *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid solution to be optimum. Higher concentrations caused a slight decrease in the absorbance, which might be attributed to self-coupling of the diazotisable amine.

Effect of acidity on diazotisation: The hydrochloric acid concentration for diazotisation was varied over the range 0.03–0.60 M, and 0.45 M HCl was found to give maximum colour intensity. Higher acid concentrations changed the colour of the dye to yellow resulting in a decrease in sensitivity.

Colour stability: The reddish orange coloured azo dye developed instantaneously under the optimised condition and remains stable upto 72 h.

Beer's law, sensitivity and reproducibility of the method: Beer's law holds good in the range 0.10–12 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of nitrite. More concentrated solutions can be diluted to bring them within the operational range of the instrument. The optimised reagent concentrations are sufficient for up to 12 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of nitrite provided alkalinity is kept optimum. The apparent molar absorptivity (referred to nitrite) and Sandell's sensitivity in the region of least photometric error were found to be $3.4 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.001 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

Under the optimised conditions, the reproducibility of the method was checked by performing eight replicate determinations of 1 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of nitrite over a period of eight consecutive days. The mean absorbance, standard deviation and relative

standard deviation were found to be 0.740, 0.002 and 0.25% respectively.

Interferences: The effect of diverse ions that often accompany nitrite was tested by carrying out determination of 25 μg of nitrite in the presence of each of these ions (concentration $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in parenthesis) in a final volume of 25 ml is as follows: Na and K (4000), Ca^{II} (200; 1 ml of 10% EDTA as masking agent), Cd^{II} and Mg^{II} (100; 1 ml of 10% EDTA as masking agent), Mg^{II} (10), Pb (80), Hg^{II} (40), Cu^{II} (20), Fe^{III} (20; 1 ml of 10% Na-K-tartrate as masking agent), Mn^{II} (5), Mn^{II} (20; 1 ml of 10% EDTA as masking agent), Co^{II} and Cr^{VI} (8), Ni^{II} (20; 1 ml of 10% EDTA as masking agent), Sn^{II} (2), sulphate (4000), sulphide (0.4), sulphite (5), bicarbonate (200), carbonate (80), chloride (3640), fluoride (40), iodide (200), nitrate (200), phosphate (100), acetate (200), and ammonia (100); the amount of diverse ion causing an error of less than 2% in the determination.

The method seems to be tolerant towards both cations and anions (with the exception of sulphide and tin), being more tolerant towards anions. The tolerance limits for cations such as Fe^{III} , Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Cd^{II} , etc. have been enhanced by using masking agents.

Application: In order to check the possible analytical application of the proposed method on real samples for the determination of nitrite in water, the extent of recovery for different amounts of added nitrite per 25 ml of sample solution was found out experimentally. The results obtained were linear and identical with those of the calibration graph obtained for distilled water. Table 1 shows the results which indicate that the method is reliable.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF NITRITE IN TAP WATER*

Sl. no.	Nitrite added $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$	Nitrite found** $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$	Mean recovery %	Relative standard deviation %
1.	2.5	2.5 ± 0.1	100.5	3.14
2.	5.0	5.0 ± 0.1	100.4	1.81
3.	10.0	10.1 ± 0.1	101.1	0.89
4.	25.0	25.3 ± 0.2	101.3	0.82
5.	40.0	40.1 ± 0.2	100.3	0.58

*Mean of five analyses, 20 ml sample, tap water gave no test for nitrite. **Mean $\pm$ standard deviation.

The proposed method is superior to most of the modifications of the Griess method owing to its simplicity, rapidity, freedom from pH-effects, temperature independence, broad range of nitrite determination, stability of the azo dye, less interference and avoidance of a lengthy extraction steps.

Table 2 shows the comparative performances of the spectrophotometric methods for the determination of nitrite.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF PROPOSED METHOD WITH SOME GRIESS MODIFICATIONS FOR DETERMINATION OF NITRITE

Reagent	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	ϵ $\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	System	Determination range $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
4-Aminobenzoic acid ^a	519	3.5×10^4	Aqueous	0.1–1.3
4-Aminobenzoic acid ^b	499	3.2×10^4	Aqueous	0.1–1.5
4-Aminosalicylic acid ^c	520	1.47×10^4	Aqueous	0.1–3.0
Indole ^d	530	9.5×10^3	Aqueous	0.5–2.0
4-Nitroaniline ^e	515	5.2×10^4	Aqueous	0.02–0.4
8-Aminoquinoline ^f	465	1.2×10^5	Extractive	0.0125–0.4
8-Amino-1-naphthol-5-sulphonic acid ^g	550	2.5×10^3	Aqueous	0–12.8
4-Nitroaniline ^h	550	3.8×10^4	Aqueous	0.03–1.1
<i>p</i> -Aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid ⁱ	495	3.4×10^4	Aqueous	0.1–1.6

^aRef. 9. ^bRef. 10. ^cRef. 11. ^dRef. 12. ^eRef. 13. ^fRef. 14. ^gRef. 15. ^hRef. 16. ⁱPresent work.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Evans Chemetics, New York for a gift sample of *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid. Thanks are also due to Mr. A. C. Saraswat, Director, Mr. B. N. Tikoo, In-charge, Chemistry Groups and Mr. D. Narasimhan, In-charge, NER Chemical Laboratory of Atomic Minerals Division, for facilities. Thanks are also due to Dr. S. K. Tiwari, Reader, and Dr. H. P. S. Rathore, Senior Research Fellow of Chemistry Department, A. M. U., Aligarh for valuable suggestions.

References

- J. GABBAY, Y. ALMOG and A. E. DONAGI, *Analyst*, 1977, **102**, 371.
- W. LIJINSKY and S. S. EPSTEIN, *Nature (London)*, 1970, **225**, 21.
- E. SAWICKI, T. W. STANLEY, J. PFAFF and A. D'AMICO, *Talanta*, 1968, **10**, 641.
- J. B. FOX, *ORC Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1985, **15**, 283.
- P. K. TARAFDER and D. NARASIMHAN, Proc. Fourth National Symp. Indian Soc. Anal. Scientists, Analytical Sciences for Environmental Studies, 1987, p. 81.
- P. K. TARAFDER and D. P. S. RATHORE, *Analyst*, 1988, in the press.
- S. E. ALLEN, "Chemical Analyses of Ecological Materials", Blackwells, Oxford, 1974, p. 203.
- R. B. LEW, *Analyst*, 1977, **102**, 476.
- S. FLAMERZ and W. A. BASHIR, *Mi rochem. J.*, 1981, **26**, 586.
- W. A. BASHIR and S. FLAMERZ, *Talanta*, 1981, **28**, 697.
- S. FLAMERZ and W. A. BASHIR, *Analyst*, 1981, **106**, 243.
- S. A. RAHIM, N. A. FAKHRI and W. A. BASHIR, *Microchem. J.*, 1983, **28**, 479.
- E. E. GARCIA, *Anal. Chem.*, 1967, **39**, 1605.
- A. FORIS and T. R. SWEET, *Anal. Chem.*, 1965, **37**, 701.
- P. K. DASGUPTA, *Anal. Lett.*, 1984, **17**, 1005.
- J. NAIR and V. K. GUPTA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1979, **111**, 311.